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Large-Scale Land Transformations and Changing Sociality among the Wampar in Papua New Guinea

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ABSTRACT

In the Markham Valley of Papua New Guinea, a Biomass Energy company is currently transforming the landscape by planting thousands of hectares of eucalyptus trees to offer a 'carbon-neutral' way of electricity generation. The company operates in concert with local Wampar landholders, offering jobs, land rents, and business opportunities. This large-scale land transformation from grassland to eucalyptus forests impacts social relations, especially those regulating access to land, and creates more and novel social conflicts within and between kin groups. By presenting four ethnographic portraits, I show how access to and exclusion from land, jobs and monetary benefits are differentially experienced, and how people negotiate these novel effects of 'intimate exclusion' occurring in their midst. There are clear trends towards alienation and exclusion of some people from land to which they formerly had access. Customary claims to usage rights are abrogated except for the primary owners of the land, and sometimes even members of the landholding lineages are deprived of receiving monetary benefits from these enterprises. Access to land, jobs and business opportunities are now governed mainly by social relations with the main decision-makers and proponents of the eucalyptus project.

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Introduction

In most parts of Melanesia, social relations are predicated on and deeply enmeshed in people's ties with the environment in which they live and the land they cultivate (Bamford 1998; Leach 2003; Schneider 2012). In this article, I will explore what happens to this form of sociality once the land and relations to land are transformed due to the impact of large-scale capitalist projects, such as large-scale tree plantations. My case study focuses on the Wampar in the Markham Valley of Papua New Guinea (PNG), where a Biomass Energy company called PNG Biomass is currently transforming the landscape by planting thousands of hectares of eucalyptus trees that will subsequently be used as fuel for a wood-fired power plant to generate so-called 'carbon-neutral' electricity. The

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company operates in concert with local Wampar landholders and offers sought-after jobs, land rents, and business opportunities. This large-scale land transformation has wide-ranging impacts on social relations, especially those regulating access to land, as it both deepens prior and creates novel social conflicts within and between kin groups.

I will first situate the relations between the Wampar and their environment in the broader literature of society-environment relations, before using four ethnographic portraits to show the effects of these large-scale transformations. Then, I will focus on how access to and exclusion from land, jobs and monetary benefits arising from the project are differentially experienced. I will use the concept of ‘intimate exclusion’ developed by Hall, Hirsch, and Li (2011) to highlight the contested nature of this process, and to draw parallels with similar processes elsewhere.

In analysing processes of agrarian transformations in Southeast Asia, Hall, Hirsch, and Li (2011) define the concept of exclusion as a social process leading to a transformation of land relations based on four powers: regulation (by the state), market, force in the form of violence, and legitimation. Through exclusion, former, current, or potential users of land are denied access to land through relations of power. But the authors also stress, that exclusion is not only negative, as there is no land use or land access without a certain form of exclusion, and that exclusion is thus constitutive for establishing productive relations to land. They differentiate between six different types of exclusion, one of which is the so-called ‘intimate exclusion’, in which villagers exclude social intimates, *i.e.* their kin or neighbours, from using parcels of land as a strategy to accumulate capital. They point out that while ‘intimate exclusion’ might be contested, as it ‘inserts market principles into transactions between intimates’ (Hall, Hirsch, and Li 2011, 166), such processes often develop with surprising speed. As I will show, ‘intimate exclusion’ in the case of the Wampar occurs through leasing out land to the company for the planting of eucalyptus trees, which prevents other uses of the land, and gives the male decision-makers in each lineage more power to regulate access to income opportunities derived from the land than was previously the case.

Society-Environment Interactions in Papua New Guinea

For many people in Papua New Guinea, the environment in which they live is more than just a background to their lives. It is part and parcel of who they are, the root and backbone of their being a person, and intimately involved in producing relations between people. As Leach (2003) shows for the Reite people, understanding kinship relations is impossible without considering the role that land plays in nurturing people and thus enabling the generation and maintenance of kin relations in the first place: ‘Persons, specified by the relations they have to other persons who nurture them, and to the place in which this nurture occurs, are connected through sharing the source of the nurture itself – placement’ (Leach 2003, 212). In addition, the landscape is not empty but full of the traces of the work of ancestors and spirit beings that are recounted in myths and histories and that stand in a close relationship with the living (Hirsch 2006; Jorgensen 1998; Telban and Vávrová 2010).

To illustrate the intimacy of these relations between people and their environment, Halvaksz (2020) introduces the concept of ‘placeperson’ for the Biangai in Morobe Province. Just as the concept of ‘natureculture’ by Haraway (2003) links human and non-

human worlds, ‘placeperson’ denotes a close interconnectedness of place and personhood. Land among the Biangai is literally expressed as ‘cared-for-ground’, while at the same time, the ground takes care of and nurtures those that grow from these relationships. As Halvaksz (2020, 6) writes:

Places across the landscape, the flora and fauna that adorn it, as well as the layers of soil, the rivers that cut through them and the minerals that are revealed are more than part of the Biangai landscape. They are also part of what it means to be Biangai and what I’m calling placepersons. ... placepersons force us to examine the blurring boundaries of place and subjectivity as places and persons mutually care for each other.

This way of connecting and being connected with the land is increasingly threatened by the encompassment of Papua New Guinea societies by the capitalist market economy and extractive industries. Leach, who observed an increasing worry of Reite people in Madang that their land might be taken away, despite the absence of any concrete plans of alienation, explains this by the fact that the ‘relationship Rai Coast people have had with land is being translated into one where economic value is taking precedence over other value, and thus their ownership of land as a form of property is coming to the fore’ (2011, 301). As he explains, people are increasingly concerned with extracting economic value from their land by making large gardens and carrying the produce for hours to markets to sell for comparatively little money, even though the money earned is at the moment supplementary and not necessary for subsistence. That the state of Papua New Guinea guarantees ownership of customary land is insufficient to counteract this worry and this tendency to see everything in economic terms. After all, the state can only recognise a very narrow sense of ownership in the form of property rights, and not the multitude of other types of belonging that are part of indigenous lifeworlds. There is thus a disconnect between indigenous forms of understanding and relating with the environment, and forms of valuing land mainly in economic terms, an imbalance that tilts more and more in favour of the latter.

Halvaksz (2020) also acknowledges the destructive forces of capitalism that threaten to rip apart places and persons mainly through urban migration and employment outside the community so that people lose connections to place, but also by generating conflicts about rights to land itself. At the same time, though, he considers the ongoing strong connection people have with land as an asset that enables them to weather the deprivations brought about by capitalism. Ultimately, he remains hopeful for those who remain rooted in their place, and who themselves believe that people will always return to the life-giving qualities of the relationship they have with the environment and each other:

Biangai subjectivities are transformed in their encounter with both mineral extraction and conservation, as well as ongoing entanglements with coffee and other cash crops, but it is their connection to place that maintains their sense of hope and their connections with each other. ... They hope to maintain their connections to place, while improving the quality of *community* life. (Halvaksz 2020, 175)

Introducing the Wampar

The concept of ‘placeperson’ is also apt for the Wampar in the Markham Valley of Morobe Province in Papua New Guinea. The Markham Valley is a 20–30 km wide flat

valley surrounded by high mountain ranges. The vegetation mainly consists of a grass savannah interspersed with fire-resistant trees, some old-growth forests along the main water courses and patches of huge rain trees that were introduced with cattle farming in the 1960s and 1970s. The Wampar living in the Markham valley are an ethnolinguistic group of about 20,000 people living in eight villages not far from Lae, the second-largest city in Papua New Guinea. I conducted fieldwork in the villages of Dzifasing and Tararan, situated about 60–70 km away from Lae, in the years 2009–2010 and 2016–2017.

The people of Dzifasing and Tararan are the descendants of those first Wampar that crossed the Markham River from the south to the north sometime in the second half of the nineteenth century and expanded into this wide valley. Ancestral stories tell of a series of movements down the Watut Valley, a unified village of all Wampar on the southern side of the Markham River near present-day Mare, and then a split, in which some clans crossed over the river (Fischer 2013). These ancestors of today's inhabitants fought against the Adzera speakers to the west further up the valley, against Uri speakers in the foothills to the north, and other Wampar further east, and were successful in claiming a large expanse of land. A rough estimate puts the total land area at 60,000 hectares.

Today it is said that at the onset, individual men claimed tracts of grassland and forest in the name of larger, clan-like patrilineal groupings called *sagaseg*. The importance of these *sagaseg* as corporate groups has disintegrated over the course of the twentieth century through pacification, Christianisation, and the encompassment of the Wampar by a capitalist market economy. It is only in the interactions with state agents and representatives of mining and plantation companies that the notion of the *sagaseg* has recently reasserted itself (Bacalzo, Beer, and Schwoerer 2014). Nowadays, the landholding group for specific parcels of land is usually an extended lineage (*mpan*) of varying depth, named after an eponymous ancestor one to three generations in the past. At the same time, there are often overlapping rights and different orders of ownership, ranging from ownership rights to land, the trees growing on the land, or usufruct rights to gardens and settlements.

As in other parts of Papua New Guinea, the Wampar landscape is not only populated by flora and fauna and people but also by the beings significant in myths and history. For example, despite the relatively recent conquest of the land lying north of the Markham River by the Wampar in the second half of the nineteenth century, there are several spirit places (*ram a rop*) all over the territory of Dzifasing and Tararan. Those spirit places always belong to specific *sagaseg*. Often consisting of notable landmarks, like hills, sections of creeks, former settlement sites, or clumps of bamboo or sago thickets, such places are generally avoided or then approached reverently only by members of the corresponding *sagaseg*, as it is said that the ancestor spirits dwell in them and could harm non-members. Besides ancestral spirits, there are also a lot of stories about nature spirits (*dzob mamafe*) that can take the shape of people, animals, bright lights at night, or whirlpools or logs floating in the Markham River (*mois katu*). These *dzob mamafe* have seen a similar trajectory to the importance of *sagaseg*: first still often told in the 1970s, they have become less known by the 1990s (Fischer 1994). With the new large-scale developments, they have become more prevalent again, because of their probative value in land disputes, but possibly also because of the spirits' close relations with the land that is now being transformed, threatening them directly.

In 2016, one *sagaseg* adamantly refused the construction of a quarry to supply road-building materials, despite a lot of compensation money offered. This quarry might have impacted a nearby cave that only *sagaseg* members could see, which is the dwelling of a spirit snake associated with their *sagaseg*. They argued that the snake and the history it represents are too important to be sold for money. Companies operating in Papua New Guinea, therefore, need to be aware of such human-spirit-place entanglements. During the impact assessment phase of the project, PNG Biomass has, among other surveys, also commissioned a cultural survey that established 43 locations of significant cultural and archaeological value within the project area, among them many *ram a rop*. Consequently, these locations are now excluded from plantation development plans wherever possible and would only be disturbed with the consent of the landholders (Erias Group 2017).

Transformations in land ownership have a long history among the Wampar. In the 1950s and 1960s, large tracts of grassland were alienated from the Wampar by the Australian colonial administration, which bought land from some lineages to lease it out to white farmer-settlers. About 30% of the total land area was thus alienated, mostly far away from the two main settlements and along the foothills. This first phase of alienation is only hazily remembered. It is often unclear who was paid how much. Still, it was often portrayed as a warning to the current generation that their uneducated forefathers were duped and sold off their land in exchange for cars, tractors, and trucks, which quickly broke down.

Patrol reports from the time show that this alienation was not conflict-free. In 1955, villagers of Dzifasing refused to sell more land to a patrol officer. The stated reason was that they had already sold much land without benefiting from it, as the land purchased by the administration was still not leased out to Australian settlers for farming (Seale 1955). One of the expected benefits from the sale to the state was that people could establish new social relations with these Australian farmers, who then would hire locals as labourers, offering a cash income otherwise difficult to achieve. By the late 1960s and early 1970s, about half a dozen white settler families planted peanuts, sweet potatoes, onions, tobacco, and corn and were farming cattle and pigs (Leahy and Ashton 2004).

The Wampar have a long record of engaging in businesses of their own: various agricultural schemes, mostly centred around cattle, chicken and cash crops, and transport (as owners of small trucks and buses). That land and the cultivation of land can generate a cash income has thus long been known (Fischer 1996; Lütkes 1999). In 1979, the Department of Agriculture and Livestock initiated a large-scale cattle ranch on Dzifasing land, which was in the hands of a landowner company composed of twelve lineages that contributed land to the scheme. Although mired in years of financial mismanagement, it still exists today. Quite a number of Dzifasing men hold or have held positions in this company (as directors and trustees). The company pays out a monthly dividend of 400 Kina¹ to each of the twelve lineages.

Many Wampar have become comparatively affluent in the latter part of the twentieth century through the production and sale of betelnut. Areca palms were an ideal crop suited to the Wampar environment. The labour input in betel nut production is fairly low: nursing and planting the palms requires a moderate initial effort, but as soon as they are past the seedling stage, the only labour needed is the climbing of the palms and the harvesting and packaging of the nuts. Areca palms were planted in orchards

or intercropped with the dominant staple (banana) in subsistence gardens. With steady—indeed, increasing—demand for this mildly addictive stimulant and relatively consistent if seasonably fluctuating market prices, areca production sufficed to allow households from lineages with even comparatively small landholdings to generate a comparatively good income, and contributed to the affluence of Wampar households by Papua New Guinea standards. Betel nuts were either sold in bulk to traders from the highlands or transported to urban centres and sold in retail (see Sharp [2013, 2019] on the betel nut trade and the role of the ‘40-mile market’ in Dzifasing as a betel nut trading hub).

In 2007, however, an unidentified areca palm pest afflicted the whole area: all the orchards were affected and have still not fully recovered. The palm trunks dried up and became brittle, the flowers dried out, and strong winds sometimes decapitated the top of the palm and killed it. As a result, the Wampar had to switch to a range of other economic activities and livelihood strategies, some that they had tried before, others completely novel, to supplement their subsistence agriculture of bananas and coconuts. In Dzifasing, people increased the production of garden and field crops for sale at the main market in Lae or the local roadside markets. By 2016, their thriving business of offering food, refreshments and produce to passing motorists on the Highlands Highway running through the village had attracted the attention of the local Member of Parliament, who funded a modern market building. Additionally, they have invested in the production of cacao for export.

The Eucalyptus Plantation

All these activities are currently supplemented and overtaken by the opportunities offered by PNG Biomass, a subsidiary of Oil Search, the largest oil and gas company in Papua New Guinea (which has recently merged with the Australian oil company Santos). PNG Biomass plans to convert about 18,000 hectares of what the company calls ‘degraded and underutilized Kunai and exotic grassland’ into fast-growing eucalyptus plantations (PNG Biomass 2021a). The trees will be harvested after 4–7 years, after which they will re-sprout from the roots for another two to three cycles. The wood of these trees will subsequently be used to fire two 15 MW power plants to generate ‘clean, renewable and sustainable’ electricity for the national power grid (ibid.). The planning for this project started in 2010, with initial trial plantations of only a few hectares.²

The company first approached a few prominent men in the village to determine whether they would be willing to lease small patches of land for these trial plantations to establish the project’s feasibility. These initial proponents then convinced others also to contribute little patches of land, and PNG Biomass started to hold information events in the village in which they explained the project. In the end, representatives of 42 lineages in Dzifasing and Tararan signed Memorandums of Understanding stating their interest in leasing portions of their land to PNG Biomass to develop plantations. The company so far has only been operating with so-called ‘Clan Land Use Agreements’ that have to be renewed yearly. But it is planning to establish Incorporated Land Groups on the *sagaseg* level that will then register their land under the Voluntary Customary Land Registration scheme, which allows land leases to the company for longer-term periods of up to 30 years. At the same time, PNG Biomass established a Landowner Business Group in 2017 that will eventually take over the running of the plantation.

This business group comprises all lineages involved in the project as shareholders, and its board is composed of influential local proponents of the project. However, as mentioned elsewhere (Schwoerer 2022), the project's aims and benefits were often only poorly understood (the financial benefits were often overestimated), and there was an atmosphere of rumours and speculations regarding the project.

During my field research between April 2016 and January 2018, PNG Biomass started ramping up tree planting significantly. While they had about 350 hectares planted by July 2016, by the end of the year, it was 450 hectares, and by the end of 2017, it had increased to around 2000 hectares. The company is in the process of having both the re-forestation and the electricity generation project certified to issue carbon credits according to the so-called 'Gold Standard for the Global Goals', a carbon credit standard supported by WWF, IUCN and other environmental organisations. Consequently, PNG Biomass (2021b) touts on its website that its biomass power plant 'is expected to displace fossil fuel generation of more than 4 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions over the life of the project.' The impetus behind this project is thus connected to global discussions on carbon reductions as a measure to mitigate climate change.

Like in the REDD+ forest conservation project in Central Suau in Papua New Guinea (Pascoe 2021), where people feared that the project was a pretext for stealing their air and land, most Wampar are only hazily informed about the precise aims of the biomass eucalyptus project. Initially, PNG Biomass was mostly promoting the project as being focused on creating jobs and securing electricity for the national grid. They also distributed a few energy-efficient stoves with built-in heat-to-electricity converters with a LED light and charging points for cell phones. Many people thus hoped that this project would finally allow them to electrify their houses. Some even assumed the electricity would be free, as it would be generated from the trees growing on their land.³ The fact that carbon credits will be part of the project was long kept away from the public. An in-married man from the Sepik living in Dzifasing, who was well informed about REDD+ projects elsewhere in PNG, finally told villagers about the potential to earn extra money through carbon credits. This information led to suspicions that PNG Biomass would keep this money for themselves or that they only invest in this project to get tax credits.

Once the carbon credit accrediting phase of the project was more advanced, PNG Biomass attempted to inform the population about the connections between the eucalyptus trees, climate change, and carbon credits in awareness meetings in the village, with only moderate to meagre success. While it should, in principle, not be too difficult to translate concepts like 'climate change' or 'carbon credits' to Tok Pisin (the local lingua franca), many explanations were too removed from the everyday lifeworld of the people in the Markham Valley. Experts of the carbon credit accrediting company flown in from overseas (two young female university graduates from Medellín, Colombia) tried to explain these concepts with the help of posters and local translators. The simplified message after translation went along the following lines: climate change is mainly due to factories in developed countries emitting too much pollution into the air, and as trees clean the air, thus cooling the world, the factories are happy to pay money to PNG Biomass for planting trees. The unfortunate use of the Tok Pisin word *win* for air (which means both air and wind) led to fears about how the Wampar will soon be bereft of cooling breezes in the Markham Valley. It remained also unclear how the clean air (or

wind) generated by the trees should flow to the countries affected by polluting industries. People reported that they saw hovering lights over the trees at night, which led to speculations that some large flying contraptions somehow suck up the air generated by the trees to sell it overseas. These rumours were possibly sparked by PNG Biomass previously using a drone to capture promotional pictures and videos.

While this paper focuses mainly on the effects of these eucalyptus plantations, it also needs to be mentioned that the Markham Valley currently hosts several additional large-scale projects. The Papua New Guinean palm oil company New Britain Palm Oil Ltd., through its subsidiary Ramu Agri-Industries Ltd., is planning to lease 5000 hectares of land from local landholders in Dzifasing and Tararan for oil palm plantations. In addition, they have taken over Markham Farming Company Ltd., which had already planted 4000 hectares of oil palms on state land near Dzifasing. The oil palm and eucalyptus projects are sometimes in direct competition over land. Some landholders who were disappointed with the eucalyptus project have already withdrawn their MoU and are now working with the oil palm company. In other cases, the same piece of land is claimed by two or more lineages, each wanting to lease the land to the other company (Schwoerer 2022). Another large-scale project is the prospective Wafi-Golpu copper/gold mine up the nearby Watut Valley with a planned access road and pipeline through the Markham Valley to Lae. And lastly, the Japan International Cooperation Agency is funding the building of a new high-voltage electricity transmission line through the same area.

Four Ethnographic Portraits

How does this large-scale transformation of the environment in the form of eucalyptus plantations now impact local social relations? I want to illustrate some of these processes by presenting four ethnographic portraits of villagers from Dzifasing.

David Riring: One of the Main Proponents of the Project

David Riring⁴ is a man in his mid-50s with adult children in their 20s. He was one of the pioneers of the plantation project. By 2017, he had already planted about 100 hectares of eucalyptus trees. This corresponds to about a quarter of the land he and his brothers collectively claim as their own. As mentioned before, access to land among the Wampar is wrapped up with membership in relatively small social groups, patrilineal lineages (*mpan*) with a depth of no more than two to three generations, and not on the level of also existing named patrilineal clans (*sagaseg*). Usually, in each lineage, a few middle-aged men with adult children make the important decisions concerning lineage land. In the case of David's kin group, he is the most prominent of these men.

David, as the signatory of the lease agreement with the company, receives a yearly rent (initially 400 Kina, and since 2017, 200 Kina per hectare) for leasing his land to PNG Biomass. He has invested part of his income in a second-hand tractor, which he uses to plough fields for new plantations as a subcontractor for the company. David is also a board member of the 'Zif Faring Business Group', which will take over the operation of the plantations in the future. David thus profits handsomely from these changes, both financially and in terms of increased social status. He said he is happy to work

with a company that values the local population and invests heavily in relations with landowners. David also is quite fond of the opportunity to work side by side with expatriates hired by PNG Biomass to ascertain the feasibility of the plantations, and he is known to socialise over copious amounts of beer whenever landowner representatives gather at the PNG Biomass headquarters near Lae.

There is, however, trouble brewing as David's success has rekindled a dispute over the ownership of his land with Nganing, a cousin from another lineage. Nganing claims that David's father, Riring, who first made gardens and built houses on the land, was originally from a different *sagaseg* and was adopted by Nganing's grandfather. As his own grandfather was the original steward of the land, Nganing asserts, Riring had no right to claim the land for himself and his children, and that he, Nganing, as a direct, non-adopted descendant, is the main landowner. Adoption among the Wampar was common in the past and still occasionally occurs today, and usually meant being completely integrated into the adopted lineage. Nowadays, however, this once-accepted integration is frequently disputed, especially when it comes to land rights. David is dismayed; he accuses his cousin of greed and insolence, for his father, Riring, was given explicit and exclusive rights to this piece of land by Nganing's father. Riring and Nganing's father grew up together and respected each other as brothers. And it was only since Nganing's father's death that Nganing pursued this claim. In that sense, today's value of the land has repercussions on previously accepted forms of relating.

Martina Michael: Dramatic Loss of Food and Income

Martina is a widow, about 50 years old, with teenage children, and one of the few people to have lost some of their gardens to the eucalyptus plantations. One of her cousins, Gwanang, informed her of his plans to establish his own 10-hectare plantation just a few days before the arrival of a bulldozer who cleared the area where one of her two banana gardens was located. It was quite a sizeable garden, about 50 by 25 m. She lost all her banana plants, coconut palms and mango trees. She was furious with Gwanang, who promised to compensate her with a portion of his yearly rent, but so far, she has not received anything. She is convinced that he only said that to appease her and seems resigned to never receiving the promised compensation. Martina's brother urged her to write a list of all plants lost and demand compensation from the company, but Martina is afraid of further souring relations between her and Gwanang.

The destruction of food gardens is against PNG Biomass policy and against the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) standards that the company applies. But Gwanang apparently presented himself as the principal landowner to the company and told their representatives that the whole family had agreed to give up their gardens to plant eucalyptus trees. A few other gardens bulldozed in the same area belonged to settlers from the Rai Coast area of Madang, who live on Gwanang's land to protect his gardens from theft. They were in no position to offer any resistance neither, as their continuing right to remain on the land depended on their relations with Gwanang.

Martina now struggles to find an additional piece of garden land that her brothers, cousins, and nephews do not already use for their own subsistence gardens and plantations, or that they have not yet earmarked for future plantations. She had married Michael, an educated man from an island province of Papua New Guinea, who then

moved to Dzifasing. Her only access to land is thus through her natal lineage, not her husband's. Women among the Wampar usually retain usufruct rights to make gardens on the land of their natal lineage even after marriage, and these rights are what enabled many Dzifasing women who married outsiders to remain in Dzifasing and even transfer some of these rights to their children (Bacalzo 2021; Bacalzo Schwörer, 2012). With the new rush to plant trees, these opportunities are now severely curtailed, and some customary usage rights are no longer honoured. And while Martina's remaining garden still supplies enough food for subsistence, the destruction of her larger banana garden is a significant loss of income. Martina has a small spot at the local market, where she fries sausages and bananas to sell to customers. With the loss of her banana garden, she now must buy the bananas she fries, which cuts into her profit.

Isaiah Nanof: Job Security but Complaints About Distribution

Isaiah is in his mid-20s and a father of two small children. As he is the nephew of a prominent proponent of the project, he has been able to get one of the few permanent job positions in the project. He is employed as a tractor driver and now has a relatively good regular income, 50 Kina a day. So far, most other jobs for local villagers have been in the form of short-term casual labour, usually for 2–3 days of planting or weeding, for 30 Kina per day. The recruitment of work parties is delegated to the signatory to the lease agreement, who then often employs his kin or other dependents, leaving the work arrangements open to abuse by interfamilial power relations. PNG Biomass, in the end, had to introduce a regulation that all workers have to sign a receipt to prevent underpayment (especially to women) by the work party organisers.

Despite his job security, Isaiah remains critical of the company and suspects it does not pay enough rent for the land. He is also critical of his uncles, the older generation of decision-makers in his lineage. He is convinced they are not negotiating hard enough with PNG Biomass and that they too quickly sign off on anything the company proposes. Thus, he has been actively networking with other younger men to put together demands they want to bring forward. They are concerned that the older generation currently in power will squander all the rental income so that his generation will have to live with only the project's adverse impacts. He is particularly worried about the fumes from the proposed power plant.

Isaiah is also upset about the distribution of the yearly rent within their extended family and suspects his uncle of embezzling some of the money. The distribution of the annual windfall of rent money has already led to conflicts in other lineages. For example, a young man from another lineage, angry about his share, has felled some trees to show his displeasure. To avoid such generational strife, a few lineages have established a plantation plot in the name of every adult male lineage member so that everyone would get their rental income directly from the company.

Mimeong Tsak: Planting Melons on Other People's Fields

Mimeong is an unmarried woman in her mid-20s. Her lineage has not planted any eucalyptus trees. Her father and uncles remained sceptical about the company's proposals and decided to wait and see how other lineages fare. Her father, Tsak, said it makes no sense

to plant trees before the power plant is built, as there would be no other market for the trees. He is also concerned about the continuing loss of land to the tree plantations and potential environmental damage due to the use of herbicides. He worries that other lineages are allotting too much of their land for plantations and foresees a future in which coming generations would be practically landless, all their land taken up by plantations, and no space remaining for subsistence gardens. He also pointed out that it is already getting difficult to find good and extensive stands of tall grass near the village required for thatching houses. And he fears the disappearance of wild pigs and other animals he sometimes hunts at night.

Mimeong's brother and her male cousins are much more open to the idea of leasing their land to the plantations, as they see it as a possibility to secure their land against the claims of other lineages. In the past, there had been conflicts with members of a relatively land-poor lineage who wanted to establish subsistence gardens on the land of Tsak's lineage. Using another lineage's land for subsistence gardens was common practice in previous generations and has only fallen away with the newer relations of production. Many members of lineages that sold most of their land to the state during the colonial time, or that have land too far away from the village to be practical for a daily walk to subsistence gardens, have long relied on all kinds of other ties, be it through maternal or affinal relations or simply friendship, to access small plots for gardening on different lineages' land. However, with land increasingly being perceived as a source for the cash that is imperative for contemporary life, this practice has steadily declined in recent decades. Mimeong's cousins' hope is that if they plant eucalyptus trees along the disputed boundaries, the incursion of non-lineage members for subsistence gardens would cease. However, they have so far not been able to assert themselves against the resistance of their fathers.

For Mimeong, the existence of the plantations offers an opportunity to earn an additional income through the planting of watermelons in the ploughed rows between the eucalyptus seedlings. This practice significantly lowers the production costs of her melon business, as she no longer must pay for a tractor to plough grassland. This form of intercropping of vegetables and cash crops, mostly watermelons, cucumbers, and peanuts, with eucalyptus trees in the first year, before the trees grow too tall, was initiated by Wampar women. PNG Biomass has since presented this practice on its website as its own contribution to food security. This proclaimed food security is rather ephemeral, however, as intercropping is only possible on newly established plantations and will end once all the plantations are established.

The distribution of sought-after planting opportunities to kin, friends and clients is handled by the male lineage members who register the land with the company. Due to Mimeong's wide kin network and her pleasant nature, she gets offers for planting opportunities through her good interpersonal relations with kin and non-kin, despite her lineage not having any plantation of their own.

Discussion

These four ethnographic portraits illustrate some of the reasons why people decide to allot portions of their land to develop eucalyptus plantations. They see the project mainly as an opportunity to create a significant rental income, even to strike it rich, to

get access to secure jobs, and to profit from the electricity it will eventually generate. For some prominent men, the opportunity to attain social status as a board member or shareholder in the landowner company, to interact with expatriates and the local elite, and be hosted in hotels for meetings is also significant. Another important argument is the ability to 'mark the land' and secure it once and for all against encroaching neighbours, settlers from other parts of Papua New Guinea, or other lineages claiming the same piece of land. The idea of combating climate change, so prominent in the company's promotional material, is not at all part of Wampar calculations.

These four portraits also show how a former work-based economy is transformed into a mixed economy with a large rent-based portion. Previously, the amount of income that could be generated from lineage land was limited primarily by each family's labour input, as no regularised form of wage labour could be employed to increase production. Other larger-scale usages of land, like cattle farming or mechanised agriculture, were dependent on sizeable inputs of starting capital. With the land now being leased out to plantations, new forms of rent have become possible for those lacking this kind of capital. Many people eagerly welcome these new opportunities, but they also foster growing disparities in wealth accumulation, access to income, and the power to monopolise some of these opportunities.

As I have shown, income based on employment by the company or the sale of crops like watermelon is directly accorded to individuals. It thus cannot be monopolised (especially after the company introduced stricter reporting requirements for salary disbursement). However, access to some of these new forms of income generation is distributed according to social relations with the main decision-makers within a lineage. And rent-based income, namely the leasing fee for the land, can and often is monopolised by those enjoying intrafamilial power, who can withhold it or invest it in nominally collective projects, like David's tractor, which differentially benefit prominent men. This pattern of income distribution has significantly increased intergenerational tensions.

I have also shown that transforming the environment from grasslands to tree plantations has led to a shift in the social relations that regulate access to land. Before, membership in a lineage was a sufficient criterion to claim some land for subsistence or small-scale market production. Now, it is only through specific social relations with the male decision-makers, who sign the lease agreements with the company and claim the plantations as theirs, that people can receive access to plantation land for intercropping. At the same time, access to land for subsistence plots is now becoming more and more restricted to only the immediate patrilineage. Social relations based on adoption, affinal, or matrilineal links might still afford access, but it is no longer guaranteed. In addition, conflicts over access to and ownership of land now proliferate both within and between lineages. The situation is aggravated by the need to acquire a collective land title for the land before it can be leased out to the plantation companies, which has increased conflicts over ownership between lineages (Schwoerer 2022).

As mentioned in the introduction, Hall, Hirsch, and Li (2011) coined the term 'intimate exclusion' for this particular type of agrarian transformation process, wherein co-villagers exclude their kin and neighbours from using land to which they formerly had access. While there is no large-scale expropriation in the case of the Wampar, there are clear trends towards alienation and exclusion of some people from the land. Customary claims to usage rights are abrogated except for those with clear patrilineal ties to the lineage claiming ownership of the land, and sometimes even members of the landowning

lineages are deprived of the monetary benefits arising from these enterprises. And access to land, jobs and business opportunities are now governed mainly by personal social relations with the main decision-makers and proponents of the eucalyptus project.

These transformation processes are only kept somewhat in check by the networks of reciprocal relations of solidarity that still exist between kin and non-kin alike, as well as by the social status that is accorded to men who spend money for collective projects. Those who earn more and are wealthier are expected to contribute more to collective duties within the lineage or *sagaseg*, or to civic obligations within the church and community. Foremost among these duties are contributions to funerary costs and funeral feasts, but also bridewealth payments, school fees for the children of close relatives, legal costs arising from court cases concerning one's lineage land, fundraising parties, or church and community events. As Beer (2022) has shown, most wealthy Wampar are still under social pressure to contribute to these causes due to gossip, shaming and blaming. The comparatively well-off even pride themselves on their civic engagement. However, she also cites the case of one individual who practically cut all social relations with others in the village to avoid the obligation to share his wealth.

This Wampar case of 'intimate exclusion' can be contrasted with the case study by Li (2014) in Sulawesi. There, a cacao boom led to the transformation of collective into private property through the planting of cacao trees on collectively owned land, while the resulting land market led to a significant increase in inequality between villagers. The initial transformation of collective to private property went mostly unchallenged because everyone was involved, because it was seen as a form of progress, and because challenging kin or neighbours about planting cacao on particular pieces of land would endanger valuable social ties. Long accustomed to an abundance of land, hardly anybody could envisage that land would eventually become scarce. Turned into private property, land could now be used as collateral, and was increasingly sold to more well-off co-villagers, particularly in times of financial need, generating stark differences between villagers who hold onto and increase their landholdings, and others who find themselves landless.

These twin processes of privatisation and commodification of land that are such a significant force in the process of 'intimate exclusion' in Sulawesi are only weakly present in the Wampar case. While leasing out the land and planting eucalyptus trees similarly excludes other claimants to the land from using it for other purposes, that exclusion does not go uncontested. Furthermore, the land that is leased out continues to be held collectively in the name of the lineage. And while there is an element of commodification in that land now generates rent by leasing it to the company, the sale of land to other lineages or even outsiders is still seen as taboo in Dzifasing, as it contravenes the strong connection between land and the collective identity of the lineage.

This taboo is not necessarily a given, however, even though customary land cannot be sold legally in Papua New Guinea and is protected by the constitution from alienation except by the state. This prohibition has not prevented actual sales from occurring elsewhere, especially around the bigger cities in Papua New Guinea, where the high demand for residential land has long led to the informal sale of parcels of customary land to outsiders (Koczberski et al. 2017; Rooney 2017). In the neighbouring Wampar village of Gabsongkeg, land sales or leases to non-Wampar who want to build a house in the 'suburbs' of Lae have been proliferating for the last twenty years. They have led to increasing social inequality and disputes within lineages over the selling of land (for

example, if one man sells lineage land without informing his brothers and cousins). This taboo on selling land to outsiders is thus only observed within certain lineages and *sagaseg* in Gabsongkeg (Beer 2017).

By contrast, every lineage and *sagaseg* in Dzifasing upholds the ban on selling land to outsiders, at least during my fieldwork. There had been an instance in which one man sold a parcel of lineage land, but his brothers and cousins chased off the buyer and told him that this land was not for sale, that they did not feel bound by the contract of sale their relative had signed, and that if the buyer wanted his money back, he would have to claim it from that particular individual. When the main representatives of another lineage sold a piece of land to a wealthy Wampar businessman from a different lineage in 2017, this was greeted with dismay. Everybody I talked to lamented the fact that ‘they sold their birthright’. The idea of a market for land thus still encounters significant resistance in Dzifasing, which supports the statement by Hall, Hirsch and Li that ‘markets are mediated by social calibrations of many kinds, and discourses that attempt to legitimate exclusion are routinely contested’ (2011, 147).

Conclusion

What happens to Wampar ‘placepersons’ if the place is transformed beyond recognition? The transformation of grassland into eucalyptus plantations is incremental and slow at first, to be sure, and was only in its initial stages during fieldwork in 2016–2017. Yet, already in 2017, there were musings, especially by those not involved in the project, about whether their village might be unrecognisable in the future. My argument here is that if places and the landscape are being transformed, then so too are relations between people and the land and, ultimately, the relations between persons themselves. This transformation sets in motion processes of narrowing the spheres of social relations that govern access to the land on which people depend for their livelihood. It creates ‘landowners’ and ‘non-landowners’ out of a set of people that previously were much more diverse, and who would have been more properly understood as stewards of the land and users of various kinds of resources emplaced on this land. The transformation of the land thus ultimately leads to a form of ‘intimate exclusion’. Access to new opportunities, be it in the form of jobs or access to plantation land for intercropping, is now governed by personal social relations with the main decision-makers and proponents of the plantation scheme in each lineage. At the same time, permanent alienation of land is contrary to Wampar customary practice and social relations. And while the leasing of land is, technically speaking, not a permanent alienation, the transformation of grassland into a eucalyptus plantation ensures that the land can no longer be used for anything else for at least one generation. It is highly likely that if plantations are used to exclude other claimants to certain rights, these claimants will not just give up, but seek redress, creating even further tensions and divisions within the community.

The only attenuating factor will be the fact that people continue to be enmeshed in kin and exchange networks that hold them accountable for contributing money earned from plantation schemes for the common good of these networks. Greed, individualisation, and disembedding practices are thus still bound and held in check by members in the local social formation through actions that re-embed reciprocal and communitarian relations, such as distributions at funerals and bridewealth exchanges. There is thus

still a glimmer of hope that a re-assertion of mutuality is possible in a rapidly changing socio-economic landscape that is now directly tied to the demands of globalised capitalism and the urgent need to mitigate the effects of climate change. But the pressure on land is increasing and will continue to increase in the future.

Notes

1. 1 Kina is equivalent to 0.28 US\$ or 0.26 Euro.
2. The first power delivery was planned for 2020. After numerous delays, the company experienced a massive setback in May 2021, when PNG Power cancelled the Power Purchase Agreement with PNG Biomass that it had signed in 2015 (Business Advantage PNG 2021). At the time of writing, it is unclear what this means for the project's future. There are indications that the electricity-generation plans have been shelved, and the plantations have been repurposed into a carbon offset project (Nangoi 2022).
3. While some households along the main Highway and in the old part of the village already have connections to the rural electricity grid, most homes in Dzfasing and Tararan are without electricity. This is because a connection to the grid is rather expensive, and PNG Biomass has no plans to connect households in the communities to the grid.
4. All names used in this article are pseudonyms. I have retained the Wampar (and general PNG) naming convention that people often have several names (both traditional and biblical/western) and that the surname is the first name of the father (or the husband in the case of married women). See Fischer (2000) and Bacalzo (2016) for the importance of names among the Wampar.

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